

MUSIC BOUNDARY DETECTION USING LOCAL CONTEXTUAL INFORMATION BASED ON IMPLICATION-REALIZATION MODEL

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we propose a novel melodic boundary detection method using the analysis results of the Implication-Realization (I-R) Model as features of machine learning. Melodic boundary detection is a task for identifying perceptual boundaries inside a note sequence, such as the phrase endings. An input feature that can express melodic expectation is important for detecting perceptual boundaries. Thus, we propose a melodic boundary detection method that incorporates features based on the I-R model, a model of local melodic expectation. To investigate the usefulness of the I-R features, we studied the impact of the I-R features on melodic boundary detection performance. The results showed that the addition of the I-R model improves the boundary detection F-measure by three points, exceeding the previous state-of-the-art.

1. INTRODUCTION

Melodic boundary detection is an important problem in music information retrieval. Boundaries are key information for understanding how humans perceive music, and can be applied to systems such as music structure analysis, performance expression, and plagiarism detection.

Designing features that represent melodic perception is critical for detecting perceptually sensible boundaries. Several studies have focused on features based on gestalt principles, such as the LBDM [1], the Grouper [2], and the GPR in the Generative Theory of Tonal Music [3]. These methods concentrate on the proximity and similarity in terms of temporal events, such as note duration, onset, offset, and inter-onset intervals (IOI). In addition, another study has focused on lyrics as a representation of cognitive structures perceived while listening to music. Previous research has demonstrated that incorporating melodic perception-representing features into machine learning algorithms leads to an improvement in boundary detection performance [4].

We believe a model of melodic expectation will complement existing features in boundary detection. For example, the Implication-Realization (I-R) Model [5, 6] is a cognitive musical theory that analyzes melodies by classifying

the expectations that arise during the perception of these melodies. Since melodic boundary is a result of how humans expect a melodic sequence, we expect such a model of melodic expectation to complement existing features for boundary detection.

This paper introduces a novel approach to melodic boundary detection, using a feature based on the I-R model. Our method uses such a feature as the input to a recurrent neural network, inspired by the state-of-the-art supervised learning method for boundary detection [7]. The contributions of this research include: (1) presenting a novel method for expressing melody expectation as input features in machine learning, (2) investigating the efficacy of the I-R Model in boundary detection through its reliance on expectation, and (3) achieving state-of-the-art results in boundary detection on the ESSEN folk song and MTC datasets.

2. RELATED WORK

In previous methods, the use of features that represent melodic perception based on gestalt theory was investigated, but it only considered one aspect of music. According to gestalt theory, perceptual elements are grouped together to form a single perceived whole in the process of perception. In melody, two kinds of gestalt can be considered, one related to time and the other related to pitch. Time-related gestalts have been studied through methods such as LBDM [1], Grouper [2], GPR in GTTM [3], and Δ IOI [8]. These methods can be described using rules and provide a large number of analysis results, which have been utilized by some boundary detection methods [8, 9]. On the other hand, methods that focus on pitch-related gestalts, such as the lyric-based system [4], are limited in number due to the high cost of both person and time involved in creating the data. In this research, we can get a large amount of data related to pitch expectations with our I-R analyzer.

3. IMPLICATION-REALIZATION MODEL

In this section, we review the I-R model. The I-R model is a cognitive music theory that analyzes melodies by considering gestalt. It focuses on the direction, similarity, and proximity of notes sequence to analyse melodies. We describe the basic concepts of the I-R model, the rules for conducting its analysis, and examples of analysis.

3.1 Implication-Realization model

The basic structure of the I-R model is comprised of event triplets, where the first two events generate an implication,

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Figure 1. The implication caused by PID and PRD.

and the remaining event assesses the implication. Narmour explains the implication through two hypotheses [6, p.3]: (1) When the same events $X + X$ of a given melody are similar, the listener subconsciously or consciously infers some repetition of X (define (1) $X + X \rightarrow X$). Sequences such as "C-C-C" when X is perceived as a pitch and "C-D-E" when X is perceived as an interval establish Hypothesis (1). (2) When events are different ($X + Y$), the listener subconsciously or consciously perceives some implied change in event Z (define (2) $X + Y \rightarrow Z$). Sequences such as "C-D-E" is perceived when X is perceived as a pitch.

There are principles for classifying any pitch triad as an implication-realization or an implication-denial. These principles are referred to as the Principle of Intervallic Difference (PID) and the Principle of Registral Direction (PRD), and they focus on the interval and direction of the notes composing a triad. These principles have parameters: qualitatively classified pitch (large, small, equal) and direction. The pitches implied by PID and PRD are as follows, as shown in Figure 1. The PID states that a small interval implies the same interval, approximately \pm two semi-notes, and a large interval implies a small interval than it. The PRD states that a small interval implies the same direction, and a large interval implies a different direction. The I-R model categorizes a triad as implication-realization if both principles are satisfied, and implication-denial if only one principle is satisfied.

When analyzing melody according to the I-R model, we use finely categorized triads based on contour, rather than just implication-realization or denial. The I-R model refers to the triads as symbols composed of eight types (Fig. 2). The Symbols are named based on their contour as P (Process) for stepwise, D (Duplicate) for repetition, and R (Reversal) for skipwise. These three symbols satisfy the PID and PRD, making them implication-realization symbols. On the other hand, the implication-denial symbols are named with satisfied principle-based prefixes. If only PID is satisfied, it's named IP(Intervalic Process) or ID(Intervalic Duplicate), if only PRD, then VP (Registral Process), VR (Registral Reversal). Also, the same symbol type is assigned regardless of note direction due to the unchanged implication produced.

Figure 3 shows results of the I-R analysis performed on actual melodies. In the figure, (a) shows the first three measures of the German folk song "Ein Männlein steht im

Figure 2. The I-R model has eight symbol patterns, which are denoted by notes filled in blue (for realized implications) or red (for denied implications).

Figure 3. Example of the same I-R analysis result assigned to different melodies. Brackets represent the location of the I-R symbol.

Walde," (b) shows the same melody transposed to a minor key, and (c) shows the melody arranged in the Ryukyu scale. Typically, the results of the I-R analysis are presented using brackets and symbol names. Here, the bracket indicates the range of note sequences assigned to a symbol with a minimum length of three notes. Additionally, the overlap of brackets indicates that multiple symbols are assigned to a note, as seen in the first note of the second measure in (a).

The effectiveness of the I-R analysis is an abstraction of pitch and interval taking into consideration musical groups. In the I-R analysis, we can represent all notes using eight I-R symbols. Hence, it is possible to consider melodies with different constituent notes as congruent in terms of contour, such as in figures (a), (b), and (c). Also, the analysis result is a way of representing the location of expectations within melodies. Therefore, the analysis represents musical groups such as motifs and phrases in addition to the contour that was previously considered in traditional abstraction.

3.2 Implementing an I-R model-based analyser

Here, we describe the implementation of the I-R model, which is an improvement over a previous method [10]. The I-R analyzer has three modules: symbol location estimation, symbol classification, and explicating implicit analysis rules. Furthermore, the analyzer achieves a recall, precision, and F-measure of 0.87 in comparison to excerpt 64 of Narmour's analysis examples from [6].

Figure 4 shows the processing flow of the I-R analyzer. The system is composed of the symbol location estimation unit and the symbol assignment unit and the explicating implicit analysis rules unit. The system receives onset, pitch, and beat strength from a melody and outputs the I-R symbol location and types. Firstly, the I-R analyzer estimates the durational closure to get the candidates for sym-

Figure 4. Overview of the I-R analyser.

bol location from the onset. Then, these candidates are prioritized by the beat strength to determine the order in which symbols are assigned. On the other hand, the symbol classification module defines a symbol assignment map to determine the symbols assigned to triples. Secondly, the I-R analyzer performs to explicate implicit module to reproduce Narmour’s analysis examples. To reproduce Narmour’s analysis examples, it is necessary to perform the I-R symbol assignment of any length. With these operations, the I-R model analyzer outputs the location and type of the I-R symbols.

3.2.1 Symbol location estimation

The clue for estimating symbol location is closure. The closure is a note at which no implication arises from the sequence of notes occurring or where the implication is weakened; in other words, a closure is a pitch event that triggers a grouping boundary. Specifically, a closure can be detected by a change in pitch interval, direction or note value, or the occurrence of a strong beat, etc [6]. Thus, the symbol location is a range that does not cross any closures. In previous studies aimed at formalizing the I-R model, the estimation of symbol locations has been carried out using durational closures [11, 12].

We use IOI to estimate durational closure. Our proposal integrates previous methods for closure estimation that have focused on pause and changes in note duration. The proposed method replaces the focus feature with IOI while maintaining the same rules as previous methods. We consider a note as a closure if its IOI increases by at least a factor of two compared to the preceding IOI.

To determine triplets assigned symbol, we establish a prioritization based on the beat strength for all notes excluding closures. The beat structure is deemed useful in estimating symbol location as it affects the formation of melodic grouping perceptions [13]. Hence, we prioritize triplets that start with strong beats, weak beats, or downbeats as the symbol location. In case of overlapping triplets starting with strong beats, weak beats, and downbeats, we priori-

Figure 5. Symbol assignment map with threshold set to six semitones. The symbols enclosed in squares indicate the symbols that appeared in Narmour’s analysis examples.

tize the triplet starting with the stronger beat as the symbol location.

3.2.2 Symbol classification

The PID and PRD rules for symbol assignment to triplets have an ambiguous parameter. The parameter is a threshold that distinguishes between small and large intervals. Figure 5 shows the distribution of symbols obtained with six semitones as a threshold. The symbol assignment map represents the symbols assigned to triplets, the horizontal axis represents the interval between the first and second notes and the vertical axis between the second and third notes. The blue cells in the figure represent pitches equal to the threshold, with different symbols defined on either side of the threshold. On the other hand, the symbol assignment map with a fixed threshold cannot cover many of Narmour’s analysis examples. Narmour’s analysis examples are represented by squares in Figure 5. A major difference between symbol assignment map and Narmour’s analysis example is the relationship between the threshold and the symbols. In the former, different symbols are defined on either side of the threshold, while in the latter, symbols like P, R, IR, and VR exist that are defined across the threshold. Therefore, it is difficult to reproduce the analysis examples while maintaining the consistency of PID, PRD rules and a fixed threshold.

We propose a symbol assignment method that utilizes multiple thresholds to define a symbol assignment map by multiple trials to cover as many of Narmour’s analysis examples as possible. In this method, we select the best threshold for each trial to define a symbol assignment map that accurately covers the greatest number of Narmour’s analysis examples. Once each trial is completed, we fix the symbols defined by the selected threshold. This process continues until all possible thresholds have been used

Figure 6. Proposed symbol assignment map. The regions painted in gray indicate Narmour’s analysis examples, where the proposed method was unable to correctly cover.

or a symbol assignment that correctly covers the remaining Narmour’s analysis examples cannot be found. As a result, we obtain a symbol assignment map that correctly covers as many of Narmour’s analysis examples as possible.

Figure 6 shows the symbol assignment map obtained when using the thresholds [6, 0, 2, 10, 1, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 11, ..] obtained by the above operation. The coverage rate for Narmour’s analysis examples improves from 69.3% of the conventional method [14] to 88.2%. Note that there are cases that cannot be covered by the proposed method in principle. One of them is the symbol assignment for triads that do not satisfy PID and PRD. There are triads with consecutive repeated notes for the first and second notes and a large interval between the second and third notes. According to the naming rule of the I-R symbol, these triads should be assigned the symbol VD, but it is not possible to assign it due to the symbol is not defined in the original I-R model. The other case is when multiple symbol assignments are made to a single triad. The proposed method assigns symbols based on rules, therefore only a unique symbol can be assigned to a single triad.

3.2.3 Explicating implicit analysis rules

Firstly, we introduce criteria for assigning symbols to each note. The symbol location estimation module presents a method for determining the sequence in which symbols are assigned to all triads, excluding those that cross the closure. Without constraints, the module would assign symbols arbitrarily to all eligible triads, which would result in reduced accuracy in comparison to Narmour’s analysis examples. To address this, we established a termination criterion for symbol assignment, stipulating that symbols must be assigned to all triads, except those that cross the closure.

Secondly, we present rules for adjusting the length of the

I-R symbols. While a standard I-R symbol consists of three notes, sometimes symbol’s length exceeds four or more (Figure. 3). This occurs when overlapping symbols result in an amplified implication, a phenomenon limited to symbols P and D due to their composition of triples consisting of intervals in the same direction and of similar semi-tones. To assign four or more length symbols, we merge symbols of the same type when the former’s start to the latter’s end, if the end of the former symbol occurs after the start of the latter.

4. PROPOSED METHOD

In this study, we present a boundary detection approach that incorporates contextual features. The use of an input feature that captures melodic perception is crucial for accurately identifying perceptual boundaries. Thus, we introduce a melodic boundary detection method using features derived from the I-R model, a model of local melodic expectation. Additionally, the model used for inference is based on a recursive neural network, inspired by a state-of-the-art technique for supervised boundary detection [7].

4.1 Features

To consider the local context information, we propose a novel feature representation based on the I-R model, in addition to conventional features like the IOI, beat strength, pitch and the interval from the previous note. The proposed features include (1) *directional features* derived from the I-R analysis and (2) *durational features* that reflect the underlying concept of the I-R model.

The *directional feature* detects local implications and realizations or denials within a melody. Our hypothesis is that the end of the I-R structure in a melody corresponds to the end of a phrase, which represents a global sense of termination. Therefore, we propose a binary feature representation of the end of the I-R structure that may reflect phrase boundaries, as shown in Figure 7. Generally, the I-R model consists of eight symbols, however, to take into account the influence of different note directions on boundary detection, we use 15 symbols that differentiate between upward and downward directions.

The *durational feature*, inspired by the I-R model, expresses the implications of the note duration. Our hypothesis is that the denial of implications regarding consecutive notes of the same length is a crucial feature for boundary detection. In this study, we propose the increase and decrease of duration as a denial of these implications regarding note values. Like directional features, these features are also represented as binary values.

4.2 Boundary detection model

The boundary detection model is based on the state-of-the-art method in supervised boundary detection task [7], consisting of a recurrent neural network, followed by peak-picking and thresholding modules. The input to the model is from the beginning to the end of the melody. The output is the location of all boundaries in the melody. The

Table 3. Comparison of error rate increments when using shuffled features on PFI.

MTC/MTC		MTC/ESFC		ESFC/ESFC		ESFC/MTC	
IOI	0.412	IOI	0.401	IOI	0.438	IOI	0.409
Beat Strength	0.144	Beat Strength	0.147	Beat Strength	0.261	Beat Strength	0.169
P_{down}	4.15e-2	P_{down}	3.25e-2	$Duration_{up}$	3.20e-2	P_{down}	3.40e-2
Pitch	2.11e-2	Interval	1.91e-2	P_{down}	2.41e-2	$Duration_{up}$	2.34e-2
$Duration_{up}$	1.89e-2	$Duration_{up}$	1.45e-2	D	1.61e-2	D	8.68e-3
Interval	1.72e-2	Pitch	1.25e-2	IP_{down}	1.15e-2	Interval	7.66e-3
P_{up}	1.51e-2	P_{up}	5.69e-3	Pitch	4.77e-3	Pitch	5.54e-3
D	1.28e-2	D	4.87e-3	Interval	3.41e-3	ID_{down}	5.48e-3
ID_{up}	7.29e-3	R_{up}	4.67e-3	VP_{down}	3.32e-3	IP_{up}	4.64e-3
IR_{up}	4.59e-3	ID_{up}	3.50e-3	IP_{up}	3.22e-3	IP_{down}	4.01e-3
$Duration_{down}$	4.54e-3	IR_{up}	2.56e-3	$Duration_{down}$	1.68e-3	P_{up}	3.78e-3

for both conditions and tested for significance using F-test with a significance level of 0.01. Hereon, the combination of training and test data used to calculate each evaluation value is indicated using the ”/” symbol, such as MTC/MTC.

In the case of MTC/ESFC, the F-measure using I-R was 0.8067, and without was 0.8061 ($F = 9.90, p = 0.005$). In the other case of ESFC/MTC, the F-measure using I-R was 0.785, and without was 0.782 ($F = 0.40, p = 0.52$). The result shows a significant difference in ESFC/MTC, and no significant difference in MTC/ESFC. We think this is because the ESFC dataset contains folk songs from various regions and diverse compositions, which might have enabled better learning of the relationship between the musical sequences.

5.3.2 Importance of each feature

We conducted Permutation Feature Importance (PFI) analysis to evaluate the contribution of the proposed features to the boundary detection performance. The PFI can calculate the contribution of each feature without modifying the model architecture or the learned parameters. The evaluation is based on the increase in error resulting from permuting the order of each features. The greater the increase in error, the more impactful the feature is considered to be. It is important to note that the error magnitude serves as a rank for the contribution of the features to the analysis, but does not reflect the actual magnitude of the contribution made by each feature. In the experiment, we computed the average of 10 trials to reduce the impact of a random permutation.

Table 3 shows the difference between the permuted features. The values in the table are sorted in descending order. The results indicate that IOI and Beat Strength are important features in all combinations. These features are considerably more important than other features and the results show that permuting IOI leads to a decrease in evaluation values by 40 points. On the other hand, features frequently used in music information retrieval, such as Pitch and Interval, have approximately the same importance as the I-R features. Additionally, the results show that certain symbols are important in the proposed features. For example, symbols P_{down} and $Duration_{up}$ are commonly

important features in all combinations. The results also indicate that the importance of symbols changes based on their direction. For example, in all combinations, the importance of symbol P_{down} is higher than that of P_{up} . We can also observe the same trend in ID symbols.

6. DISCUSSION

Figure 8 shows an instance of the boundaries that can be deduced using the I-R features, as well as the results of the corresponding the I-R analysis. The boundaries identified with the utilization of the I-R features are represented by orange dots, while those detected without the utilization of the I-R features are depicted by blue dots. The correct boundaries are depicted by green dotted lines. This example exhibits a case where the termination of the I-R symbol ID_{down} aligns with the boundary. It is believed that incorporating information regarding the ending note of the I-R symbol led to the accurate identification of the boundary.

To assess the impact of the introduction of the I-R symbols on boundary detection, we analyzed the relationship between the ending positions of the symbols and the boundaries in the datasets. Figure 9 presents the total number of the I-R symbols in the datasets and the number of the symbols that matched with the boundaries and the end of the symbol. The lighter-colored bar graph depicts the total count of the I-R symbols observed in the datasets, while the darker-colored bar graph represents the number of symbols that matched the boundaries. The data suggest that certain the I-R symbols are effective in boundary detection. For instance, the symbols such as VP_{up} , IR_{up} , and R_{up} exhibited a high proportion of matching with the boundaries, despite their low frequency of occurrence. In contrast, the

Figure 8. A boundary detected using the I-R features.

Figure 9. The frequency of the I-R symbols in datasets and the number of symbols that match the boundaries.

symbols such as *P*, *IP*, and *ID* had a lower rate of matching with the boundaries in comparison to their frequency of occurrence. This implies that specific contours provide useful hints for detecting boundaries.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, we incorporated a feature based on expectations obtained from the I-R analysis into a state-of-the-art boundary detection technique. Our proposed approach demonstrated superior performance compared to prior methods across all datasets. Additionally, to investigate the usefulness of using the I-R features, a comparison of performance was made between cases where the I-R features were used and cases where they were not used. It was found that there was a significant difference, depending on the dataset. Through an investigation of the relationship between boundaries and the I-R features, we discovered that certain contours tend to appear at boundaries. In the future, we aim to further improve boundary detection performance by considering global contextual features such as repeating structures.

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